

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AGGRESSION AND LONELINESS LEVELS AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between aggression and loneliness levels among university students. The method employed is a correlational survey model, a descriptive research method aimed at identifying a specific situation. The sample consists of 100 university students, 50 women and 50 men. Data were collected using the UCLA Loneliness Scale and the Buss-Perry Aggression Scale. Pearson correlation analysis and independent samples t-test were used for data analysis. The relationship between aggression and loneliness levels among university students was found to be statistically significant.

Keywords: *Aggression, loneliness, relation with aggression and loneliness.*

Üniversite Öğrencilerinin Saldırganlık ve Yalnızlık Düzeyleri Arasındaki İlişki

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Özet

Araştırmanın amacı, üniversite öğrencilerinin saldırganlık ile yalnızlık düzeyleri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesidir. Yöntem, bir durumu tespit etmek amaçlandığı için betimsel araştırma yöntemi olan ilişkiisel tarama modelidir. Bu araştırmanın örneklemini 50 kadın ve 50 erkek olarak toplam 100 üniversite öğrencisinden oluşur. Araştırma için gerekli verileri toplamada UCLA Yalnızlık Ölçeği ve Buss-Perry saldırganlık ölçekleri kullanılarak toplanmıştır. Veri analizinde de Pearson korelasyon analizi ve Bağımsız örneklem t testi kullanıldı. Üniversite öğrencilerinin saldırganlık ve yalnızlık düzeyleri arasındaki ilişki anlamlı bulunmuştur.

Anahtar kelimeler: *saldırganlık, yalnızlık, saldırganlık ve yalnızlık arasındaki ilişki.*

Introduction

Data from studies investigating how common loneliness is, show that loneliness is not an unfamiliar situation for most of us (Duy, 2003). Peplau and Perlman (1982) define loneliness as "a disturbing, psychological state arising from the difference and contradiction between the social relationships an individual is experiencing and the relationships they wish to experience" (cited in Güven, 2017).

Aggression is an action that most people exhibit in certain situations and are affected by its consequences in various ways (Tuzgöl, 1998). Berkowitz (1987) views aggression as physical and verbal actions performed with the aim of physically or psychologically harming someone (cited in Gönültaş, 2014). Freedman, Sears, and Carlsmith (1998) define aggression as any action or behavior aimed at hurting other people. Aggression is a phenomenon that we all experience in our daily lives and whose consequences are inevitably harmful (cited in Kağıtçıbaşı, 2004).

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between aggression and loneliness levels among university students. This research sought answers to the following questions:

- a. Do the aggression levels of university students show a significant difference in terms of gender?
- b. Do the loneliness levels of university students show a significant difference in terms of gender?
- c. Is there a significant relationship between aggression and loneliness levels among university students?

METHOD

Research Model

This research utilized a correlational survey model, a type of descriptive survey method, to investigate the relationship between aggression and loneliness levels among university students.

Population and Sample

The typical case sampling method of purposive sampling was used. Research data were collected from students enrolled at Atatürk University during the 2018-2019 academic year. The population of the study consisted of students within Atatürk University. Within the scope of the research, 100 students (50 female, 50 male) studying at Atatürk University were reached, and analyses were performed on 100 data points. Data Collection Tools

In this research, the UCLA Loneliness Scale and the Buss-Perry Aggression Scale were used as data collection tools.

UCLA Loneliness Scale: Developed by Russell, Peplau, and Cutrona (1980) to measure loneliness levels in their research, it is a scale with 10 points coded in the direct direction and 10 points coded in the reverse direction. The scale is a 4-point Likert-type scale. The scale corresponds to the following answers: 1 'never experiences', 2 'rarely experiences', 3 'sometimes experiences', 4 'frequently experiences'. The highest possible score a person can receive on the scale is 80, and the lowest is 20. As these scores increase, the level of loneliness also increases. In Turkey, the validity and reliability studies of the scale were conducted by Demir (1989). In his study, Demir found the Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficient of the scale to be .96. He also found the test-retest reliability coefficient to be .94 ($p < .001$). In this study, the reliability coefficient was found to be .76. The Buss-Perry Aggression Scale (1992) is one of the most widely used aggression scales worldwide. The scale is a 5-point Likert scale and consists of 29 items. The scale aims to measure four dimensions of aggression: physical aggression, verbal aggression, hostility, and anger. The scale includes 9 questions related to physical aggression, 5 questions related to verbal aggression, 7 questions related to anger, and 8 questions related to hostility. The Cronbach's alpha value for the overall scale is .85. This value was calculated as .78 for physical aggression, .48 for verbal aggression, .76 for anger, and .71 for hostility. Internal consistency was calculated to determine the reliability of

the Turkish adapted form, and test-retest and split-half techniques were used. The Cronbach's alpha value for the overall scale in the Turkish form is .85. This value was calculated as .78 for physical aggression, .48 for verbal aggression, .78 for hostility, and .71 for anger (cited in Madran, 2012). In this study, the reliability coefficient was found to be .86. Veri Analizi

In this study, the given assumptions of normality were tested. For this purpose, it was decided to use the ‘Two-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov’ test. Pearson correlation analysis and independent samples t-test were also performed to determine the relationship in the study. The data were tested at a significance level of 0.05. Findings This section of the current research presents the results of the analysis of the data obtained in line with the research.

In order to examine whether the scores obtained by university students from the loneliness scale differed significantly according to their gender, an independent samples t-test was applied and the results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of loneliness levels of university students according to gender variable.

Gender	N	\bar{X}	Ss	T	Sd	p
Female	50	1.9870	0.3712	.041	.369	0.968
Male	50	1.9840	0.3673			
Total	100	1.9855				

As seen in Table 1, when the loneliness levels of university students were examined, no significant difference was found between the scores of female students and male students ($t(.369) = .041, p > .05$). When the averages of the students were examined, it was seen that the total average score of female students ($\bar{X}=1.987$) was higher than the total average score of male students ($\bar{X}=1.984$). In general, it was observed that the loneliness level scores of university students were low ($\bar{X}=1.99$).

An independent samples t-test was conducted to examine whether university students' scores on the aggression scale differed significantly based on their gender, and the results are presented in Table 2.

Tablo 2 Üniversite öğrencilerinin saldırganlık düzeylerinin cinsiyet değişkenine göre dağılımı

Gender	N	\bar{X}	Ss	T	Sd	p
Female	50	2.7731	0.5891	-1.230	.543	0.222
Male	50	2.9073	0.4984			
Total	100	2.8402				

As seen in Table 2, when the aggression levels of university students were examined, no significant difference was found between the scores of female students and male students ($t(.543) = -1.23, p > .05$). When the averages of the students were examined, it was seen that the total average score of male students ($\bar{X}=2.91$) was higher than the total average score of female students ($\bar{X}=2.77$). In general, it was observed that the aggression level scores of university students were at a low level ($\bar{X}=2.84$).

In order to examine whether there was a significant relationship between the scores obtained by university students from the loneliness and aggression scales, a correlation analysis was applied and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: The relationship between loneliness and aggression scores.

		UCLA toplam	Saldırganlık
UCLTotal	r	1	.246*
	p		.013
	N	100	100
Total aggression	r	.246*	1
	p	.013	
	N	100	100

* $p < 0.05$

As shown in Table 3, a significant positive correlation ($r=.246, p < .05$) was found between the loneliness and aggression scores of university students.

CONCLUSION

This research, which aimed to examine the correlation between aggression and loneliness levels among university students, yielded the following results:

A significant positive correlation was found between loneliness and aggression scores among university students. Accordingly, as loneliness scores increase, aggression scores also increase.

No significant difference was found in loneliness scores based on gender. In other words, there is no significant difference in loneliness levels between genders. When examining the total averages, it was observed that the total average score of female students ($\bar{X}=1.987$) was higher than that of male students ($\bar{X}=1.984$). Overall, university students' loneliness scores were found to be low ($\bar{X}=1.99$).

No significant difference was found in aggression scores based on gender. In other words, there is no significant difference in aggression levels between genders. When the total averages are examined, it is seen that the total average score of male students ($\bar{X}=2.91$) is higher than that of female students ($\bar{X}=2.77$). In general, it was found that university students have low aggression level scores ($\bar{X}=2.84$). In contrast to this research (Cansever, 2017; Erkiner, 2012; Eroğlu, 2009; Çelik, 2006; Tuzgöl, 1998), they found a significant difference between aggression levels in terms of gender and found that the aggression levels of men were higher than those of women.

REFERENCE

- Cansever, D. (2017). *Ergenlerde algılanan ana baba çatışması ile saldırganlık arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi* (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Akdeniz Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Antalya.
- Çelik, H. (2006). *Üniversite birinci sınıf öğrencilerinin saldırganlık tepkileri, bağlanma tarzları ve kişilerarası şemalarının incelenmesi* (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Marmara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Demir, A. (1989). UCLA Yalnızlık ölçeği'nin geçerlik ve güvenilirliği. *Psikoloji Dergisi*, 7, 14-18.
- Duy, B. (2003). *Bilişsel-davranışçı yaklaşıma dayalı grupla psikolojik danışmanın yalnızlık ve fonksiyonel olmayan tutumlar üzerine etkisi* (Yayımlanmamış doktora tezi). Ankara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara.
- Erkiner, D. (2012). *Lise 1. sınıf öğrencilerinin saldırganlık düzeyleri ile aile işlevleri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi* (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İzmir.
- Eroğlu, S. (2009). Saldırgan davranışının boyutları ve ilişkili olduğu faktörler: lise ve üniversite öğrencileri üzerine karşılaştırmalı bir çalışma. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi* 21, 205-221.
- Gönültaş, O. ve Atıcı, M. (2014). Ortaokul son sınıf öğrencilerinin öfke düzeyleri ve saldırganlık düzeylerinin bazı değişkenlere göre incelenmesi. *Çorum Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 23(1), 370-386.
- Güven, E. (2017). Güzel sanatlar lisesi öğrencilerinin yalnızlık düzeyleri ile dinledikleri müzik türü arasındaki ilişki. *Balıkesir Üniversitesi Necatibey Eğitim Fakültesi dergisi*, 16(3), 1247-1261.

Kağıtçıbaşı, Ç. (2004). *Yeni insan ve insanlar sosyal psikolojiye giriş*. İstanbul: Evrim Yayınevi.

Madran. H.A. (2012). Buss-Perry saldırganlık ölçeği'nin türkçe formunun geçerlik ve güvenirlik çalışması. *Türk Psikiyatri Dergisi*, 23()

Tuzgöl, M. (1998). *Ana-baba tutumları farklı lise öğrencilerinin saldırganlık düzeylerinin çeşitli değişkenler açısından incelenmesi* (Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Hacettepe Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Ankara.